

LAUNCHING THE ACTIVITY OF IMAGE-MAKING CENTERS TO STRENGTHEN THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN POLITICS

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Abstract. In the article, the topic that has become an urgent issue of the new Uzbekistan today, i.e. increasing the social and political activity of women, measures to strengthen their role in politics based on their knowledge and potential, is emphasized. The changes taking place in the republic, adopted laws, social and political processes were analyzed in depth. Based on the obtained information, solutions and conclusions were presented. Taking into account that the need for image-making centers that serve to increase the political literacy of women in our society and interest them in management processes is increasing day by day, recommendations were made to establish the activities of such centers based on foreign experience.

Key words: female politician, political literacy, image, image-making centers, socio -political activity, main factors, research, media training.

Enter. Today, the changes taking place in the political life of Uzbekistan indicate that the role of the Politician is increasing in the formation and operation of political power. globalization, leads to greater openness, mass-political power and society's interdependence . This, in turn, shows that the role of the politician, who is a personalized form of interaction between the government and society, is increasing.

From history, the ability and special role of women in government and society

is well known. However, the fact that the issue of women's participation in politics still lags behind that of men requires a more serious approach to this issue.

Because the participation of women in politics is their daily problems also ensures that it grows in parliamentary debates. Empowering women in public administration and providing them with the necessary resources will improve the protection of women's interests.

In this context, encouraging women's aspirations not only in business and other aspects of social life, but also in politics, gives them the ability to be powerful agents of reform, and this in turn encourages others to follow them. Today, more attention is paid to the support system for women and girls than ever before. Not only in the mass media, but also in the current legislation, new laws are being developed and implemented in this regard. As a clear proof of this, if we take paragraph 25 of the Uzbekistan-2030 strategy approved on September 12, 2023, it "Continuing the policy of ensuring gender equality, increasing the share of women in management positions by 30 percent by increasing the socio-political activity of women. Creating an environment of intolerance towards oppression and violence against women in society, women's rights and provision of legal interests..." is envisaged. It is known to everyone that the result here is not to increase the number of women, but to increase the number of women who are real mature and masters of their work.

Thinking about solutions to this agenda issue, the question arises why there are fewer women politicians than men. Similar reasons were partially highlighted at the Central Asian forum on gender equality policy reform and the presentation of the report "Uzbekistan: assessment of the gender situation in the country" held on March 27, 2024 at the Hilton Hotel.

From a local point of view, there are the following reasons why women are relatively less active in politics: the traditional role of women in society is strongly associated with rigid stereotypes, and they often find it difficult to break

away from it. This can be based on the fact that the support, sometimes physically, sometimes morally, and in many cases materially, is significantly less. In addition, "...the economic independence of women is viewed with suspicion and the employment of middle-class mothers is condemned, the work of working-class women is often considered a necessity." It is still very difficult to manage family, household and work at the same time. It should also be noted that , in many cases, as the number of children increases, a woman begins to shorten her career and devote less time to her interests.

Even in such a case, a woman can become not only a "mother" but also a specialist in her own profession as she pursues her goals based on her own desires, experience and knowledge.

Mainly, jobs in local authority management require "more overtime" from women than men. If we look at it from the point of view of mentality, the possibilities of women do not correspond to this. In order to regulate this situation and create suitable calendar jobs for women and girls, it is important to unite and support each other.

In particular, we need to create the development of networks whose goal is to increase the position of girls in local government.

In Germany, Christiane Horsch, together with other campaigners, founded the "Leaders Network of Women Community Leaders" within the local and municipal administration of Rheinland-Pfalz. Through this network, she aims to support young political women and introduce exemplary women to everyone.

We need image-making centers to adapt this experience to the conditions and culture of Uzbekistan. Political image is the basis for creating relations between politicians and voters. Centers for creating the image of politicians are organizations or firms that specialize in shaping the public image and perception of politicians. These centers often provide services such as public relations, media management, campaign strategy, speechwriting, and image consulting to help

politicians present themselves to the public.

They may also assist in marketing and advertising to promote a politician's platform or campaign. These centers play an important role in shaping public opinion and have a significant impact on the success or failure of a politician's career.

The main part. Women play an important role in forming governments, becoming leaders of political parties and being active in many areas of politics. They should cooperate with the media, with the public and with the authorities to improve their political image . For women to be successful in the political environment, they need to understand their values and opinions. The political image of a woman depends on her natural character and appearance against the local and global community. This is related to their expression of independent opinions and the free opinion of the society. Female politicians, like all politicians, should be qualified, educated and dedicated to serving the people. They must be strong leaders who can make tough decisions and advocate for policies that benefit their constituents. It is important that they are ethical, honest and transparent in their actions and decisions. In addition, female politicians should strive to be role models for other women and girls, showing that they can succeed in leadership roles and have a positive impact on society. In order to put such advice into practice, to increase the professional and intellectual potential of active women working in various fields of public administration, to prepare them for leadership, to organize short-term training in the system of the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. ' was launched. The Academy of Public Administration and its regional branches organize trainings on improving the political and legal knowledge and management skills of women in reserve for leadership, changing the moral image of educational programs, planning, team building, leadership and introducing topics of communication skills formation." became one of the main principles.

As an example, if we take the state apparatus of the United States of America. it is the administration with the largest number of women in its history. Only in 1993, women occupied more than 2500 positions in it (more than 40%). i), and 27 of them are persons appointed to high positions by the president (heads and deputies of federal agencies), including 6 members of the cabinet.

If we look at the example of new Uzbekistan, in 2017, the share of women in management was 27%, today it has reached 33%, in the ranks of political parties from 40% to 47%, in entrepreneurship from 21% to 37%. About 2,000 women are serving in leadership positions in state and public organizations. In particular, 33% of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 25% of the members of the Senate and local councils are women.

Political image creation, which can serve as the main tool for raising these results even higher. Here, not only knowledge about politics is given, but also the correct approach from the legal side to the problems that future leaders may face in the process of leadership, starting with how to behave and speak. Because today, the legitimacy of politicians directly depends on the public's assessment of the government . Image is a very common concept in psychology and refers to an emotionally charged image that is developed in the public mind and has a stereotypical character. We emphasize that, first of all, the political image is an image formed in the public mind, and mass media and mass media (media and mass media) play a decisive role in its formation. Given the rise of social media, politicians need to maintain a positive image. If people hate them, they won't vote for them, and if not enough people vote, elections can be missed and new ones created. This is a very delicate area. For example, even a small mistake made by the candidates during the elections can put their reputation at risk. In order to have a positive impact on the opinion of citizens who associate the term politician directly with men, it is necessary for female politicians to have more contact with these centers.

Summary. Political image management centers work closely with politicians to develop a plan that emphasizes what is important to improve how people perceive them and how others see them. The image includes such parameters as the political leader's constitutional characteristics (gender, age, health status, as well as appearance characteristics), brand and organization logo. Most authors working in the field of image studies emphasize that this is the most interesting aspect of the image of a political subject for a person. In addition, the image component includes the emotional-volitional state of the politician's personality, which reveals the features of willful regulation of the politician's temperament and behavior. In addition, this service provides media training, which allows the center to offer coaching techniques for interviews, speeches or debates, which would be perfect for those who want to manage their personal identity.

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